

Digitizing Healthcare: Examining Consumer Willingness to Disclose Personal Health Information in Developing Countries

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Introduction

In recent years, developing countries have been investing in IT to transform healthcare delivery. This effort to digitize healthcare is driven by the need to extend geographic access to care, and to ensure efficient collection and management of personal health information (PHI¹) required to address many of the chronic health problems (e.g., HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis) prevalent in developing countries (Lewis et al., 2012).

Research conducted in developed countries (e.g., Anderson & Agarwal, 2011) show that the digital transformation healthcare has led to heightened consumer concerns about PHI privacy. This is due to the increased risk of privacy loss through criminal attacks (e.g., hacking), and the ease with which opportunistic activities (e.g., sharing health information with third-parties) can be carried out. Lending support to the privacy threat posed by digitizing health information, a recent Ponemon Institute's (2016) study of 91 health organizations in the USA found that 90% had had a data breach with criminal attacks and malicious insiders representing the main sources of breach.

Despite the dangers of privacy loss, the privacy of consumers' PHI is often peripheral in electronic healthcare (e-health) systems development in developing countries (PNE, 2010). According to PNE (2010), developers of e-health systems assume individuals in developing countries are in so much need of healthcare that they care for little else. This assumption, however, is contradicted by studies which indicate consumer concerns about privacy in both the traditional healthcare and the emerging e-health settings. For example, studies (e.g., Dapaah & Senah, 2016) show that individuals with heavily stigmatized diseases (e.g., HIV/AIDS) hide their infection and avoid needed care for fear of the negative consequences (e.g., loss of relationships, jobs, etc.) that can result from disclosure of their infection. Also, in a recent study in Ghana, Bedeley and Palvia (2014) found that individuals are concerned about the privacy of PHI with the introduction of computer systems in hospitals. Studies in other developing countries (e.g., Kuo et al., 2014; Willyard, 2010) similarly report consumer privacy concerns regarding the digitization of healthcare.

Due to concerns about PHI privacy, individuals may resist digitization of their health information, especially when they learn they are potentially vulnerable to abuse through weak privacy protection in e-health systems. However, securing consumers' cooperation and willingness to allow their PHI to be stored in digital form is crucial to the successful digitization of healthcare. It is thus imperative to examine consumers' PHI disclosure behavior in e-health environments in which the possibility of privacy loss is significant. Toward this end, this study seeks to understand the factors that influence

¹ PHI includes any type of information that a patient submits to receive care and the information that is generated in the process of receiving care.

the willingness of consumers in developing countries to disclose their PHI in order to receive care from healthcare providers where the disclosed PHI is stored and used electronically.

Prior research on privacy and willingness to disclose information (including PHI) has produced findings that may not readily generalize to developing countries' context. For example, much of this research has been conducted almost exclusively in developed countries (Bélanger & Crossler, 2011). Here many employ tech-savvy samples as most studies used online surveys (Kokolakis, 2015). However, the majority of individuals in many developing countries have limited or no digital experience compared to those in developed countries. Consequently, their concerns and willingness to disclose PHI in a digital environment may be different from individuals in developed countries. This study thus extends the boundaries of extant IS privacy research by examining consumer willingness to disclose PHI in the e-health setting of a developing country, Ghana. The specific e-health setting considered is an electronic healthcare system (EHR) system usage within a hospital.

Theoretical Foundation

This study adopts the privacy calculus as the overarching theoretical framework. The privacy calculus is considered the most useful framework for analysing consumer privacy concerns (Culnan & Bies, 2003). The calculus perspective suggests that privacy disclosure decision results from a cost-benefit analysis in which individuals weigh the risk/cost of personal information disclosure against the benefits to be gained from disclosure. Individuals disclose personal information when the benefits of disclosure exceed or match the risk of disclosure.

The privacy calculus has been used in a variety of IS domains to examine the simultaneous impacts of contrary beliefs on privacy disclosure decisions. The contrary beliefs include factors that drive the intention to disclose (which are called drivers), and those that inhibit privacy disclosure by individuals (which are called inhibitors). Privacy risk and privacy concern are the major inhibitors usually studied in the literature. Privacy risk reflects beliefs that a high potential for loss is associated with disclosing personal information for use in digital/online environments. Privacy concern, on the other hand, refers to users' concerns about what happens to the personal information they disclose in online environments and how this information is used.

The set of drivers frequently studied include perceived benefits and trust. Perceived benefits comprise the benefits that an individual expects to gain from disclosing personal information in transactions with others. Trust reflects a willingness to assume the risk of disclosure and become vulnerable to the actions of an entity that one trusts (Culnan & Bies, 2003).

A number of gaps identified in prior research based on the privacy calculus which this study addresses are highlighted below:

- Individuals' calculation of risk includes an assessment of the possibility of loss and the potential negative consequences of loss (Peter & Tarpey, 1975). However, risk has been measured in prior research largely in terms of the former, i.e., beliefs about the possible loss of data. Consumer concerns about privacy and their eventual refusal to disclose health information are due to the impact that such disclosure may have on their daily social and economic interactions in society (Laric, 2009). The perceived negative consequences of disclosure are therefore an important factor in a patient's desire to protect the privacy of their health information and hence must be studied closely.
- The core calculus constructs are often not examined together in a single study (e.g., Anderson & Agarwal, 2011). These constructs may have differential impacts on diverse behavioural outcomes and their true relative impacts can only be ascertained when considered together. To buttress this, Bélanger and Crossler (2011) observed from a number of studies that trust more strongly predicts behaviour than privacy concern when the two constructs are examined together. This study includes all the core calculus constructs and also examines their relevant dimensions.

Conceptual Model and Method

The proposed conceptual model which expands and extends the privacy calculus model is provided in Figure 1.

The dependent variable of interest is willingness to disclose PHI. The study considers an individual's PHI disclosure to hospitals for the purpose of receiving care where the disclosed information is stored and used electronically.

In contrast to prior research, aside from the conceptualization of privacy risk as beliefs about the possibility of privacy loss (i.e., perceived likelihood of disclosure), the proposed model also considers users' expectation of the negative consequences of PHI disclosure. Reviewing the relevant literature (e.g., Laric, 2009), the impact of potential consequences (e.g., potential damage to one's social status and relationships) of PHI disclosure on willingness to disclose PHI is examined.

Following recommendations in prior research (e.g., Tan & Thoen, 2000), two targets of trust are included in the model: trust in the entity providing a service (which is a hospital in the case of this study), and trust in the electronic medium through which the service is provided; the latter is often studied in past research. Trust in hospitals refers to an individual's perception regarding the integrity and benevolence of hospitals in protecting the privacy of their PHI. Trust in electronic medium, on the other hand, includes users' beliefs that electronic storage offers a reliable and safe environment in which to store health information.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

The study includes convenience, and responsiveness as the benefit factors derived from digitizing healthcare (Krishna, 2010). Convenience concerns consumers' perception of the reduction in time and effort spent in receiving care. Responsiveness refers to perception of improvement in hospitals' readiness to provide care services to patients.

The study extends the privacy calculus model by integrating it with procedural justice (a core dimension of justice theory) to study the effect of two important antecedents of concern and trust which have received limited attention in health information privacy research: perceived effectiveness of government regulation, and perceived privacy policy. Procedural justice in the IS context reflects individuals' fairness judgements of the procedures enacted for the collection and use of their personal information (Xu et al., 2009).

One important factor that can shape consumers' perceptions of procedural fairness relates to their control over the collection and use of their information (Culnan & Bies, 2003). It is expected that government regulations that provide effective protection against privacy breaches on consumer PHI

can give consumers a sense of control over the handling of their PHI. This will likely alleviate consumer concerns about privacy and increase their trust in hospitals and in the electronic medium through which hospitals provide care services. If consumers also perceive privacy policy of hospitals as offering adequate protection of their PHI privacy, they are likely to consider the information practices of the hospitals as fair. Consumers are therefore less likely to be concerned about PHI privacy. However, they are likely to trust hospitals and their use of e-health systems.

To test the proposed model, the study adopts a scenario-based survey method. Given that the technology innovation (e-health), which is the focus of this study, is nascent in many developing countries (Lewis et al., 2012), a scenario-based survey approach is appropriate as it enables the study of an emerging phenomenon (i.e., possible and plausible future) “without being constrained by the timing of the study or the state-of-the-art of technology” (Sheng et al., 2008). The sample for the study will be drawn from individuals living in Ghana. A diverse sample will be considered such that it reflects the general demographic (in terms of gender, age, and education) of the Ghanaian population (excluding children). The collected survey data will be statistically analyzed using the partial least square approach to path-modeling.

In general, this study responds to the call to increase the generalizability of IS privacy research (Bélanger & Crossler, 2011) by extending its boundaries to the understudied context of developing countries. Toward this end, the study proposes and investigates a more comprehensive model (based on the privacy calculus) aimed at providing a more in-depth and nuanced understanding and insight into the relative importance of the various factors (both drivers and inhibitors) that influence PHI disclosure intentions. By maintaining the underlying theoretical framework of the privacy calculus which has been used extensively in analyzing concerns about privacy in extant research (Culnan & Bies, 2003), the study will evaluate the model’s applicability to explaining privacy behaviour in developing countries. It is hoped that understanding both drivers and inhibitors of PHI disclosure will help practitioners such as government, and healthcare providers to better respond to and address the concerns that people have regarding their PHI, and take actions that can encourage the disclosures needed to enable better healthcare provision for their constituents.

Given that differences in cultures, values, and laws may cause differences in information privacy perceptions and its impacts (Bélanger & Crossler, 2011), the findings of the study may not generalize to developing countries whose cultures, values, and laws are significantly different from that of Ghana.

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